

Influence of Intrinsic, Extrinsic and Interpersonal Factors on Vocational Choice of Secondary School Students in Ogidi Education Zone of Anambra State

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of intrinsic, extrinsic and interpersonal factors on vocational choice of students using descriptive survey research design. A total of 600 students were randomly selected from ten schools that constituted the sample for the study. Three research questions guided the study. The instrument used for data collection was validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation and Guidance and Counseling. The instrument was tagged Influence of Intrinsic, Extrinsic and Interpersonal factors on Vocational Choice of Students Questionnaires (IIEIVCSQ). The reliability and validity of the instrument were obtained. Weighted mean were used to answer the research questions. The major findings of the study identified was that intrinsic and extrinsic factors mainly have strong influence on vocational choice of adolescents in secondary schools while interpersonal factors has less influence on the adolescents choice of vocation. Therefore it was recommended that counsellors should not be loaded with school work so as to enable the counsellors to explore the interests, strength and weaknesses of students choice of vocation in relation to similar subjects related to their special abilities and interests. There is also the need to establish Guidance and Counselling units in all secondary schools to be manned by these experts.

Key words: *Intrinsic, Extrinsic, Interpersonal, Vocational choice, Students*

Introduction

Unemployment has been a major problem facing the youths today. Youths are seen roaming the streets especially in developed cities in Nigeria. This could be the resultant influence of unemployment. Nigerians unemployment could be categorized into two, the older unemployed and the younger unemployed. According to Awogbenle and Iwuamadi (2010) citing Manpower Board and Federal Bureau of Statistics showed that Nigeria has a youth population of 80 million representing 60% of the total population of the country. Out of this number 64 million of youths are under employed thus negating the National policy on education (2004) which stipulated that everybody should benefit and contribute to national development. This unemployment and under employment is a great threat to the national development as it could lead to frustration and dissatisfaction, thus yielding low productivity and civil unrest in the

country. Some of these youths could be ready tools to cause youths restiveness as they are not pre-occupied with jobs that could engage them (Muhammad & Yusuf, 2016), Then confirming the adage that says “ An idle man is the devils workshop”.

According to Durosaro and Nuhu (2012), observed that most undergraduates and graduates experience problems in the course of studies due to the fact that they were not properly guided in their choice of subjects combination, whereas in the secondary school, students who are not well guided may find themselves in subjects for which they possess no ability and aptitudes to study. These students may end up being frustrated and or end up with jobs that do not fit their personality type and consequently drop out of job (Holland, 1985).

Vocational choice is one of the most important and difficult choices in an individual's life. It also has critical influence on many aspects of professional and social life of an individual. Vocational choice can make or mar an individual throughout his/her adult life. An individual's choice of vocation influences their economic empowerment, their social relationship as well as their political relationships in the society. Increase in the gap between the number of graduates in some professional and academic fields and real demand on the National labour market is one of the core challenges of many nations and educational system. For instance the labour market is still saddled with graduates who cannot be gainfully employed and could cause youth restiveness that can jeopardize the National development.

The word vocation is derived from the Latin verb “Vocare” which means “to call”. This vocation is a calling to a way of life. Iram, Afrina and Atika (2012) posit that vocation is a type of occupation especially one for which a person is qualified to perform. Vocation is like a call in response to a certain work especially in religious career. A vocation is an occupation for which a person is suited or qualified to do. It is also the inclination to undertake a certain kind of work. Vocational choice is therefore an intended profession in which a person is intrinsically and extrinsically attracted to be trained or qualified leading to employment for which one earns a living and job satisfaction. Vocational choice, according to Bubic and Ivaniservice (2016), is a significant issue in the developmental life of adolescents as it is associated with positive and negative psychological, physical and socio-economic inequalities that may culminate into individual adulthood. Counsellors are therefore expected to equip adolescents with necessary personality characteristics that will enable them make effective, efficient, and well informed decision and choices (Oguzie, Ani, Obi & Onyegirim, 2018). By so doing, such individuals could live a fulfilled life. Erikson theory of psychosocial development maintained that adolescents at this stage are neck deep in search of personality identity. If an individual's life of vocation is incongruent with his personality job satisfaction may likely be actualized. Also Kunem (2013) observed that when an individual is properly guided in choice of vocation, his identity, wellbeing, job satisfaction and stability in life may likely be assured. Conversely those who were not properly guided may choose wrongly, get frustrated and drop out of job.

Researchers have suggested different factors that may influence choice of vocation. According to Carpenter and Foster (1977) Hewit (2010) and Holland (1985) posited that all vocational influencing factors stem from either intrinsic, extrinsic or interpersonal factors/dimensions. Intrinsic dimensions are set of interests related to the profession and its role

in the society. Researchers like Gokuladasi (2010) and Kunnen (2013) observed that youths who are motivated by intrinsic factors are influenced by their interest in a given profession that are personally satisfying. The intrinsic factors could be decision originating within the individual as well as actions driven by interest, curiosity or pleasure. These include job satisfaction, personality traits and learning experience (Raymond & Deci 2000).

The intrinsic factors include personal interest, self efficacy, outcome expectation and professional development opportunities. According to (Owie 2003), as cited by Kumazhege (2017) posited that interest is a significant factor in an individual's choice of vocation but academic achievement or requirement may influence interest positively or negatively. Choi and Kim (2013) observed that interest could sustain the individual to excel and be satisfied in a chosen vocation. According to Gokuladas (2006), students from urban centres are likely to consider their personal interest before societal interest when making vocational choice. Amani (2013) has it that students self interest is an important deciding factor in choice of vocation as this will aid the students to derive job satisfaction. Most students choose vocation they have interest as well as the ones they believe they can study and work on depending on their self concept and perceived self-efficacy. Such students believe they have what it take to study such profession even when they fail; they continue to be resilience in their studies until they graduate in such profession (Hui & Len 2018).

Outcome expectations and professional development motivate students to choose a particular vocation. The benefits that is derived from a given vocation can trigger an individual to choose a given course/profession as well as what the job can offer in the future (Anold, 2014). In Nigeria some students choose certain vocation as a result of fat salary they think such vocation can offer even when they do not have what it takes read such course.

Extrinsic factors refer to the desire of social recognition and job security. This is the benefit associated with certain occupations (Shaffner, 2015). Some researchers have observed that many youths tend to choose career based on what the job/vocation can be associated with such as job security, job accessibility, job satisfaction and financial remuneration (Edwards & Quinter, 2011). Most adolescents are being observed imitating different vocations they admire. Some even go to the extent of dressing like them. Such students derive satisfaction by showcasing themselves as a colleague already in the field.

Researchers such as Wust and Leko Simic, (2017) reported that financial remuneration was the highest influential factor in choice of vocation. Income counts/matters most in choice of career especially students who are independent of their parents as they take care of their financial responsibilities. In addition, prestige statuses attached to some occupations can pull students to choose such occupations. In Nigerian situation, students in science class tend to choose medicine as their first choice of vocation. This is because of the prestige and dignity attached to medical profession. The same is applicable to youths in South Africa, as the youths wanted prestigious jobs that would earn them good living and respect in the society. Job accessibility also influences choice of vocation. Some youths chose vocation they have access to rather than occupation they preferred or read especially in this period of unemployment.

Interpersonal factors consist of activities of agents of socialization in one's life and this includes family members, teachers/educators, peers etc. Students who are influenced by interpersonal factors take into consideration the opinions of family members and significant others in the family. Such students are willing to subdue their personal interest at the expense of such member's advice. Agorwala (2006) reported that fathers have significant influence on students' vocational choice especially in patriarchal society while in matriarchal society the reverse becomes the case. In his study most of the student's fathers were professionals which may be the underlying factors in motivating these students into their father's profession. In addition to this parental values, pressure and family obligation influences students' choice of vocation. They put emphasis on specific choice of career through encouragement and persuasion. Most of these students were reported to choose what their parents want just to please them (Nyako-Sampson, 2015).

Peer influence exerts a great force on adolescents. As children begin to relate to outsiders, children's attachment to their parents begin to wane as a model for conformity and reference group. As soon as they start school, their peers seem to take over. This play group (peer) is made up of play mates, friends or people within the same age brackets who share the same values and ideas. Research has shown that peer group is a reliable instructional technique that can enhance social learning and social skills of adolescents (Uroko 2010). In addition peer pressure has a significant role on influencing vocational choice. These adolescents discuss so many topics in their gatherings that may influence their vocational choice. Some of them may lure others to choose a certain vocation especially their friends. Peer influence is a tool for developing career decision making and career opportunities among youths. According to Naz, Saeed and Waseen (2014), their study indicated that peer influence shapes ones perception and attitude towards decision making including choice of vocation (Bett, 2013).

The power of peer group cannot be over emphasized when family relationship is weak, especially when parents are not available to lend support. These young people can easily turn to their peers for affiliation or closeness whether positive or negative on decision making including choice of vocation. Through these processes adolescents can influence their peers in their choice of vocation as well as through adolescent compliance and acceptance within the group. Kumazhege (2017) in support of these maintained that peer pressure influenced some students in making decision that influenced their life today. Most of these peers discuss certain issues such as sexuality, choice of vocation and social skills of interpersonal relationship in their gatherings. They can influence each others in their discussion such as vocational choice and choice of subject combination. Another research posits that peer influences others to go into more challenging tasks as one compares with other peers in making career decision(Naz et al 2014).Some of these students may decide to choose a vocation as a challenge because a friend or a certain peer is on training or in the university pursuing such vocation.

Career guidance counsellor provides students with vocational information that will enable them to make choice of career. But unfortunately some schools as witnessed by the researchers could not provide this information. School counsellors also encourage/advice students to combine subjects that seem to be in line with their abilities, aptitudes and interest.

Through these services guidance counsellors can influence students choice of vocation but unfortunately most schools in Nigeria do not have guidance counsellors that could direct these students even where they are available they are not recognized to operate.

Teacher Educators also have significant influence on vocational choice of students especially in the situation where by the parents are illiterates. These students tend to depend on the teacher/educator for information and support (Cheung at al 2013, Anold, 2014). However, there is no literature evidence on the influence of intrinsic, extrinsic and inter-personal factors on vocational choice of students in Nigeria. Most research evidence are from outside Nigeria whose socio-cultural environment is different from Nigeria. Therefore, there is need to explore the influence of intrinsic, extrinsic and interpersonal factors on vocational choice of students in Ogidi Education Zone of Anambra State.

Statement of problem

Vocational choice could have an indelible mark on the individual's life. Wrong choice of vocation could land an individual into life difficulties that may last for years while right choice of vocation can have a positive effect on the individual and ensure a better adjustment for the individual and society in the future. Therefore there is need to explore various factors that could influence students choice of vocation to enable the students be informed and make right choice of vocation to achieve better for themselves and the society. Most researchers have suggested factors likely to influence students' choice of vocation such as intrinsic, extrinsic and interpersonal factors.

However most research evidence are from outside Nigeria whose socio-cultural environment is different from Nigeria setting. Therefore there is need to investigate the influence of intrinsic, extrinsic and interpersonal factors on vocational choice of students in Ogidi Education Zone of Anambra State .

Research questions

1. What is the influence of intrinsic factors on vocational choice of secondary school students?
2. What is the influence of extrinsic factors on vocational choice of secondary school students?
3. What is the influence of interpersonal factors on vocational choice of secondary school students?

Method

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised all the public secondary schools in Ogidi Education Zone of Anambra State. Ogidi Education Zone is made up of Oyi Local Government Area, Idemili North and South Local Government Area. Thirty one schools were involved in the study. At least ten (10) schools from each local government area filled the questionnaires. Twenty students were randomly selected to fill the questionnaire thus given 620 students. Finally 600 questionnaires were returned.

The instrument for data collection was filled; Influence of Intrinsic, Extrinsic and Interpersonal factors on Vocational Choice of Students Questionnaires' (IIEIVCSQ). The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by two educational experts from the department of Guidance and Counselling and Measurement and Evaluation of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. They pointed out corrections and the researchers used these in adjusting the instrument accordingly. The reliability and internal consistency of the tests were ascertained through pilot testing of the instrument on 20 students from secondary school in Onitsha another Education Zone. Test re-test method was employed while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to establish stability yielding a value of 0.88. The weighted responses were structured on four point rating scale of strongly agree (4 point) agree (3 point) disagree (2 point) and strongly disagree (1 point). Any item with a mean of 2.50 and above was regarded as agreed while a mean score of below 2.50 shows disagreement of the respondent with the item.

Results

Table 1 Intrinsic Factors

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	X	DECISION
1	My vocational choice is based on my interest.	300 1200	250 750	10 20	40 40	600 2010	3.35	Agreed
2	I choose my vocation based on the subjects I like best.	250 1000	200 600	85 170	65 65	600 1835	3.05	Agreed
3	I will display my special abilities on my vocational choice.	300 1200	200 600	65 130	35 35	600 1.965	3.27	Agreed
4	My choice of vocation is similar to my school subjects that are easy for me.	350 1400	200 600	35 70	15 15	600 2085	3.47	Agreed
5	My choice of vocation is based on the benefits I will derive from the job.	315 1260	245 735	15 30	25 25	600 2050	3.41	Agreed
6	Vocational choice of mine will offer me opportunity to apply my skills and knowledge I will acquire.	300 1200	220 660	50 100	30 30	600 2140	3.26	Agreed
7	My choice of vocation will offer me opportunity to grow in the job/profession.	215 860	245 735	75 150	65 65	600 1810	3.01	Agreed
8	My choice of vocation gives me personal joy.	300 1200	200 600	80 160	20 20	600 1920	3.3	Agreed
9	My choice of vocation motivates me to study harder.	320 1280	200 600	40 80	40 40	600 1920	3.2	Agreed

10	My choice of vocation shows my kind of person.	200 800	200 600	150 300	50 50	1750	2.9	Agreed
Grand mean							3.216	

Data in table 1 indicated that all the items (1-10) have mean ratings above the cut off mean of 2.50. The mean scores ranges from 2.9 to 3.47. The overall mean of 3.216 is also above the acceptable mean of 2.50. It thus revealed that intrinsic factors such as subjects that lead to choice of vocation, benefits likely to be obtained in the vocation and interest are the main intrinsic factors that pull students to a certain vocation. Other factors such as opportunity to use special abilities, application of learnt skills and knowledge, professional growth, personal satisfaction, motivation and self actualization all have influence on choice of vocation.

Table 2 Extrinsic Factors

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	X	DECISION
1	My choice of vocation has job security in the future.	305 1220	200 600	85 170	10 10	2000	3.33	Agreed
2	I choose my vocation because of salary associated with it.	400 1600	100 300	60 120	40 40	2060	3.43	Agreed
3	My vocational choice is based on the prestige associated with it.	300 1200	150 450	100 200	50 50	1900	3.16	Agreed
4	Vocational choice is based on availability of job.	300 1200	200 600	60 120	40 40	1960	3.26	Agreed
5	I choose a given vocation in other to be self employed.	150 600	200 600	150 300	100 100	1,700	2.83	Agreed
6	My choice of vocation allows for flexibility(change).	100 400	100 300	250 500	100 100	1300	2.16	Disagreed
7	My choice of vocation allows offers opportunity for advancement.	300 1200	200 600	50 100	40 40	1940	3.20	Agreed
8	My choice of vocation is based on the location of the job where available.	10 40	30 120	245 490	315 315	600 845	1.40	Disagreed
9	My choice of vocation has nothing to do with prestige associated with it.	90 360	70 210	120 240	320 320	600 1130	1.8	Disagreed
10	My choice of vocation has nothing to do with the position it will give me in the society.	80 320	80 240	140 280	300 300	600 1140	1.9	Disagreed
Grand mean							2.6	

The results in table 2 shows that the grand mean is 2.6 showing that extrinsic factors influence vocational choice of secondary school students, though certain factors are likely to have much influence such as salary, job security, job availability prestige attached to the job, job advancement opportunity for self employment. While location of the job, has no influence on choice of vocation.

Table 3 Interpersonal Factors

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	X	DECISION
1	My vocational choice is influenced by my parent's advice.	400 1600	150 300	80 160	20 20	600 2080	3.46	Agreed
2	My parents choose my subjects combination for me.	300 1200	200 600	55 110	45 45	600 1955	3.23	Agreed
3	My parent's educational background influenced my vocational choice.	400 1600	100 300	80 160	20 20	600 2080	3.46	Agreed
4	I will not consider my parents advice for my choice of vocation.	80 360	20 60	100 200	300 300	600 1120	1.86	Disagreed
5	My parent's job does not influence my choice of vocation.	120 480	80 240	100 200	300 300	600 1,220	2.0	Disagreed
6	I admire a vocation where I can work together with my friends	300 1200	150 450	80 160	20 20	600 1880	3.13	Agreed
7	I do not like going into the same vocation with my friends.	80 320	20 60	150 300	350 350	600 1030	1.96	Disagreed
8	My teachers advice influenced my choice of vocation	80 320	70 210	150 300	300 300	600 1130	1.88	Disagreed
9	My teachers exposed me to vocational information/guidance.	50 200	60 180	240 480	250 250	600 1110	1.85	Disagreed
10	My school counsellor exposed us to guidance services.	60 240	40 120	150 300	350 350	600 1010	1.68	Disagreed
Grand mean							2.6	Disagreed

The results on table 3 above shows that the grand mean is 2.45 which is below 2.50 thus indicating disagreement. The interpersonal factor has less influence on students choice of vocation except factors such as parental advice, parent's choice of subject combination, parental education background and peer influence.

Discussion

The findings from research question 1 revealed that intrinsic factors have dominant influence on secondary school student's vocational choice such as interest, job satisfaction, learning experiences. This lends support to the findings of Choi and Kim (2013), Amani (2013) who maintained that interest sustains the individuals to excel and be satisfied in a chosen vocation.

Still research question 2 revealed that extrinsic factors also give a long way in influencing vocational choice of secondary school students. The study revealed that most students choose vocation based on income associated with it. This is in agreement with the findings of Shaffner (2015) and Wust and Leko Simie (2017). The researchers reported that financial remuneration was the highest influential factor in choice of vocation with particular reference to students who are on their own. Availability of job is another extrinsic factor that influence choice of vocation especially these days when unemployment is an ugly monster dealing with our youths. Many youths are ready to do any job as far as they will be employed and get paid.

The data in research question 3 revealed that an interpersonal factor does not have all that strong influence on student's choice of vocation, except parental factors. This confirms Agorwala (2006), findings that fathers have significant influence on student's career choice especially in patriarchal society while in matriarchal society the reverse becomes the case. Also, Nyako-Sampson (2015) finding also indicated that students choose what their parents want just to please them without considering their own interests. Peer pressure also influence student's choice of vocation especially where family communication is weak. These students can turn to their peers for advice. This concurs with the work of Kumazhege (2017) where as other factors like teacher and counsellor have less influence to students choice of vocation as they are saddled with teaching job that could not allow them discharge vocational guidance (Beck, 2004).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study and the discussions that followed, the researchers concluded that intrinsic, extrinsic and interpersonal factors all influence secondary school students' choice of vocation in Ogidi Education Zone of Anambra State. The intrinsic factors such as interest, similar subjects related to the vocation and use of special abilities influenced choice of vocation. Extrinsic factors such as income, prestige, job availability and job satisfaction influenced the students' choice of vocation while interpersonal factors such as parents have a strong influence on the students' choice of vocation. Finally, teacher and guidance counsellors do not have strong influence on choice of vocation. It is therefore imperative that parents interest in students choice of vocation should not undermine their children's interest. Teachers/ counsellor should not be overloaded with school work to hinder them from giving career guidance.

Recommendation

The following recommendations were made:

1. Since interest attracts individual to certain occupation. Counsellors should enhance counselling services by using vocational interest inventories to find out where students interest lies in choice of vocation and guide students towards such vocation.
2. Counselors should organize counselling services that will involve parents forum where parents will be sensitized not to impose/ choose vocation for their children.
3. The school authority should make fund available to counsellors to organize career programmes inviting professionals who are in the fields to speak to the students directly rather than using the teachers as witnessed during career days in some schools.

4. The school authority should ensure that students with counsellors embark on excursions for them to witness working conditions of certain vocations.
5. Government should fund schools through equipping and retooling of schools. School curriculum should incorporate students work industrial experience in their subjects.
6. Communities should synergize with schools to allow the skilled laborers to come and teach the students certain skills of different jobs other to reorient students about the world of works

REFERENCES

- Awogbenle, A.C. & Iwuamadi, K.C. (2010) Youth unemployment: Entrepreneurship Development Programme as an intervention mechanism. *African Journal of Business management*, 4(6) 831-835.
- Amani, J. (2003). Social Influences and Occupational Knowledge as predictors of career choice intention among undergraduate students in Tanzania'' *International Journal of Counselling and Development*, 3(3), 185 – 193.
- Agorwala, T. (2008). Factors influencing career choice of management students in India. *Career development. Int.* 13. 362-376 doi:108/13 62043810880844.
- Bett, J.C. (2013). The importance of promoting the value and the role of peer counseling among students in secondary school. *International Journal of economy, management and social science*, 2(96), 477-484.
- Bubic, A. & Ivaniseni, K. (2016). The role of emotional stability and competence in young adolescents career judgement. *Journal of Career Development*, 43, 498 – 511 doi 101177/089485316633779.
- Choi, K. & Kim, D.Y. (2013). A cross sectional cultural study of antecedents on career preparation behavior: learning motivation, academic achievement and career decision self efficacy. *J. Hosp. leis sport tour Educ* 13 19-32 doi 101016/j-jhl ate 2013.04-001.
- Carpenter, P. & Foster, (1977). The career decisions of student teacher education. *Res Pers* 23-33.
- Durosaro, A. & Nuhu, M.A (2012), Gender as a factor in the career choice readiness of senior secondary school students in Illorin Metropolis of Kwara State Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social science*, 2(140), 109-113.
- Edwards, K. & Quinter, M. (2010). Factors influencing students career choice among secondary schools students in Kisumu municipality. Kenya *J. Emerg trends Educ. Res. Policy stud.* 281-287 Available online at <http://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC13714>.
- Gokuladas, V.K. (2010) Factors that influence first career choice of undergraduate enigneers in software services companies: a south Indian experiences. *Career dev. Int.* 15 144-165 doi 10 1108/13620431011040941.
- Hewit, (2010). *Factors influencing career choice*. Retrieved from www.ehow.com on 15/02/2020 Englewood cliffs.

- Holland, J.L. (1985). *Making vocational choices a theory of vocational personalities and work*. New Jersey: prentice hall.
- Hui, K. & Lent. R.W. (2018). The roles of family culture and social cognitive variables in the career interests and goals of Asian American College students. *Journal of counselling psychology*, 65 98-109. Doi 101037/cou 0000235.
- Iram, G., Afrina, A. & Atika, B. (2012). Analysis of the factors influencing vocational decision making of university female students of masters level in university. *Academic Research International* Vol. 2 No. 2 2012.
- Kunem, E.S. (2013). The effects of career choice guidance and identity development. *Educ. Res. Inc.* 2013: 901718. Doi 10. 1155/2013/901718.
- Mohammad, S.U.K. & Yusuf, T.M. (2016). linguistic aspect of counseling and conflict resolution for national stability. *The Counsellor*, 35(122), 2016.
- Naz. A., Saed, G. & Waseem, K. (2014) Peer and friends and career decision making: a critical analysis: *Middle-East Journal of scientific Research*, 22(80), 1193-1197.
- Oguzie, A.E., Ani, D.P., Obi, B.A. & Onyegirim B.O. (2018). Effect of cognitive restructuring technique on fear tendency among secondary school students in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo state. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Publications*, 2(1), 34-38.
- Raymond & Deci E.L (2000) Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation: Classic definition and new direction. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25, 54-67 doi: 10-10006/ceps/1999 1020.
- Shoffner, M.F., Newsome, D. B., Minlon, C.A. & Watcher Moris C.A. (2015). A qualitative exploration of the STEM career-related outcome expectations of young adolescents. *J.Career Dev.* 42.102-116. Doi:101177/0894845314544033.
- Wust, K. & Leko, S.M. (2017). Student career preference: Intercultural study of creation and German students. *Econ.Sociol* 10136 – 152 doi 1014254/2071. 789x 2017/10.3/10.